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Peer Reflection using an E-portfolio Improves Students' Leadership Behaviour

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ABSTRACT

Leadership education has been conducted for first-year students of the Master's program at the Shibaura Institute of Technology's Graduate School of Engineering and Science for over ten years. Because students have limited opportunities to learn from hands-on leadership experience, we utilize a simulator to increase students' experience in a safe environment. A student is less resistant to take leadership actions following repeated practice in simulations. The program has five modules: knowledge, training by simulation, real action, reflection, and assessment. Results of previous studies showed that student leadership ability improved. This program was popular among students because of its interesting educational method and high effectiveness. Initially this was an elective subject for a small number of students, but following its success was made compulsory and is now attended by about 80 students. It became necessary to devise a way of reflection to bring educational effects to the larger numbers of students. The e-portfolio was introduced to invite students to review their behaviour. It became difficult for the faculty to provide individual feedback on e-portfolios to so many students. Looking back on experience from others is essential for improving the students' behaviour. Consequently, we introduced peer reflection, which is evaluated in this paper – the students exchanged reflections with each other based on behaviour recorded in their e-portfolios. Consistent with our hypothesis, students who tried to continually apply the new learning obtained by peer reflection in a real situation significantly improved their leadership behaviour.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1. Leadership Education Background

A leadership education program has been conducted in the Master's program at the Shibaura Institute of Technology's Graduate School of Engineering and Science since 2008. In this program, leadership is defined as an ability to grasp the emotion of team members accurately, to collaborate with them, and to appropriately develop human relationships. In addition, leadership is not an ability inherent in a special person, but is rather for everyone to exhibit and develop. The traditional leadership education only gave students' knowledge regarding leadership in the form of lectures. Many students have never been leaders in their social and school lives and a leading role is unimaginable to them. Therefore, how to apply such knowledge through action is a big issue for them. Thus, a new leadership education program was created in order to enhance students' actions, which in turn improved quality of the educational method [1] [2] [3].

1.2. Education Using Simulation

Students who lack experience have huge gaps between knowledge and action and this makes it impossible for them to immediately turn knowledge into action. Therefore, we utilize simulation as a means to bridge these gaps (Fig. 1) [4]. The simulated experiences that students acquire through repetitive practice can provide a smooth bridge to reality.

Fig. 1. Simulation Interface

1.3. Levels of Learning and Educational Achievement Goals

This leadership education has four levels: knowledge, consciousness, action, and mastery (Table 1). In contrast, the traditional leadership education only provided learning level 2, and had no curriculum designed to transform knowledge into action.

Table 1. Leadership Educational Achievement Level

Learning level		Performance goal
4	Master	Establish new behaviour by a process of trial and error
3	Act	Act in the real situation as he/she did in simulated experience
2	Conceive	Realise needs of behavioural change and improvement points of daily action to reflect on oneself through the simulated experience
1	Know	Understand necessary knowledge to show leadership

2. LEADERSHIP EDUCATION MODEL

The leadership education model (Fig. 2) is constituted of five modules: knowledge, training by simulation, real action, reflection, and assessment [5]. At the start of a program, diagnostic evaluation is conducted. Next, a student enters a cycle of skill acquisition. The first step is for students to gain knowledge in the leadership arena through lectures. Then, they utilize simulation to experience leadership actions many times. Simulation provides a safe environment in which they can try many different approaches in taking leadership in various situations. A simulation exercise has the effect of raising awareness of daily improvement and the necessity for new action as a result of self-reflection, all of which stem from the various virtual experiences.

Fig. 2. Leadership Education Model

In the next step, students as a team utilize PBL (Project Based Learning) so that the above simulated experiences can help them to show leadership. Students can apply trained leadership to actual projects, and this increases their leadership skills. It is highly effective to apply conscious leadership to a project aimed at a specific goal in limited circumstances. This education repeats both of the steps above, raising leadership abilities in an upward spiral. Furthermore, the learner reflects on the simulated experience and the action in practice, and identifies the skill correction component and the skill that needs training. In the end, students complete a comprehensive evaluation. This paper focuses on the reflection component.

3. CHALLENGES TO REFLECTION IN LARGE CLASSES

This program is popular among students because of its interesting educational method and high effectiveness. Therefore, after initially being an elective subject for a small number of students, this was introduced as compulsory for many students (about 80) (Fig. 3). It became necessary to devise a way of reflection that would provide the educational outcomes for the increased number of students. The e-portfolio was introduced to invite students to review their behaviour but it became difficult for the faculty to provide feedback to so many students after individually analysing all the e-portfolios. However, looking back on experience from others is essential for improving the students' behaviour. Consequently, we introduced peer reflection – the students exchanged reflections with each other based on the behaviour recorded in their e-portfolios.

Fig. 3. A large-scale class of about 80 students

4. PEER REFLECTION USING AN E-PORTFOLIO

4.1. Effective Use of E-portfolio

E-portfolios (portfolios handled electronically) are used widely in the field of education. Effective use of an e-portfolio allows students to reflect on their own learning and improve their continuous learning practice. This process also connects students' regular lessons and extracurricular activities, and promotes integration of learning.

4.2. E-portfolio and Student Reflection

Students recorded the results of leadership behaviour in simulated experiences and practices in the e-portfolio once a week. This process continued for six weeks. Students performed mutual reflection on the behaviour in the simulated experience and practice described in the e-portfolio in the second week of these classes. The 81 students were divided approximately into groups of six. The flow of reflection was as follows.

Personal reflection

- Describe what happened
- Record your feeling then
- Evaluate advantages and disadvantages
- Analyse what caused this.

Group reflection

- Performed in groups of six people. By taking on the role of facilitator, the group members reflected on each member.
- The facilitator posed a retrospective question on the behaviour of the members. In this case, they asked other members how to do a specific task and generated various ideas.
- From here on, everyone discussed what action to take. Facilitators were required to show leadership so that they explored the possibilities of various actions.

Personal work

- Filled in the e-portfolio with action improvement measures and specific actions to implement in the future.

5. ASSESSMENT

The following assessments were conducted to verify whether student-to-student reflection influenced student leadership behaviour.

Evaluation 1: Change in leadership behaviour frequency

Evaluation 2: Degree of useful reflection between students

Evaluation 3: Relationship between the degree of helpfulness of reflection among students and the frequency of leadership behaviour.

5.1. Evaluation 1: Change in Leadership Behaviour Frequency

Students transferred the training on the simulator to practice in the PBL exercise. Students evaluated how often 12 items of leadership behaviour (Table 2) were performed in practice. They continued this process once a week for six weeks. The behaviour frequency criteria follow: 1, all of the time; 2, some of the time; 3, hardly ever; and 4, never.

Table 2. Leadership Behaviour

#	Items	
1	I can devise my work to contribute to an activity in a project.	Goal setting and achievement
2	I can understand specific situational requirements and encourage project members to achieve their goals.	
3	I can contribute to a project and achieve results through work.	
4	I can share knowledge and technology with a project member positively, and can strengthen a mutual relationship.	Communication and problem solving
5	I can discern the cause of a problem, acquire pertinent information, and determine a solution.	
6	I can carry out activities for the smooth progress of a project.	
7	I can coordinate socially relevant research tasks and	Proposal of

	plant the seeds for scientific innovation.	ideas and planning ability
8	I can propose an idea with confidence in a timely manner.	
9	I can create a plan foreseeing short- and long-term research results.	
10	I can manage my and others' ability to cope with high pressure situations or rapidly changing environmental conditions.	Understanding the situation and building relationships
11	I can engage a project member in conversation, listen attentively and positively, and show sympathy.	
12	I can raise motivation by managing a project member's level of stress.	

5.2. Evaluation 2: Degree of Useful Reflection between Students

Whether reflection between students improved subsequent leadership behaviour was evaluated, using the following criteria: 1, very useful; 2, useful; 3, a little useful; and 4, not very useful.

5.3. Evaluation 3: Relationship between the Degree of Helpfulness of Reflection among Students and the Frequency of Leadership Behaviour

We analysed the relationship between the degree of reflection between students and the degree of improvement in leadership behaviour (Table 2).

6. RESULTS

A number of items in the leadership behaviour shown in Table 2 improved as follows. Seven items improved for students who answered "Very useful", 4.9 items for "Useful" students, 3.7 items for "A little useful", and 3 items for "Not very useful". Students who answered that the other students' reflections were more helpful had more leadership action items with higher scores (Table 3).

We also extracted the first and sixth times from the description of the e-portfolio concerning the behaviour change of students who said that other students' reflections were very useful (Table 4). In the first reflection, these students ended with a description of the activity content, but in the sixth, they mentioned the awareness from the activity and the improvement measures for the next time. As a result of the analysis of the transition of the e-portfolio description over six weeks, the following has been confirmed. The accumulation of small behaviour coordination led to small success and the acquisition of new behaviour. Also, continuous reflection over six weeks showed that students have become accustomed to observe

and monitor their cognitive processes. In addition, students learned to actively seek strategies for problem solving. These activities have led students to carefully evaluate their own growth. Furthermore, the implementation of peer reflection gave students a new perspective of self-assessment based on the opinions of others. Students need to maintain motivation for continuous reflection. It is essential for students to acquire knowledge as to the meaning, method, and effect of reflection as knowledge.

Table 3. Relationship between Effects of Student Reflection and Improved Leadership Behaviour

Effects of student reflection	Very useful	Useful	A little useful	Not very useful
Number of students	27 (36%)	38 (50%)	7 (9%)	4 (5%)
Number of improved leadership action items	7	4.9	3.7	3

Table 4. The First and Sixth Descriptions of Students' E-portfolios

	The first description	The sixth description
A	In the project exercises, I expressed the affirmation of the opinion by noting the opinion given by the members. I could encourage project members to express their opinions. However, I thought that it would be necessary to devise new ideas to allow deeper discussions.	In the project, each member worked to improve work efficiency by dividing the work. There was a lot of individual work, but when there was something I did not understand, we discussed this among members. I tried not to move in the wrong direction. As a result, we worked efficiently without going in the wrong direction.
B	As a team leader, I experienced difficulties in judging what the members could do and assigning them appropriate work. I was too attached to one job. Communication with the	I thought that the leader should have the most work, so I initially did not allocate much work to the members. I noticed that work efficiency of the members was bad. However, by

	members was not enough.	allocating work equally to each member, I was able to process tasks quickly and efficiently.
c	I thought that high-tension meetings would not have a positive impact, and I made an effort to move forward in a peaceful atmosphere from beginning to end. However, this lowered the motivation of the other members. It turned out that it was necessary to adjust the degree of tension so that the meetings could be productive.	At the meetings, we focused on what was important and what was to be prioritized. When the members' opinions were divided, we were able to select the agenda at the meeting smoothly by firmly conducting a factor analysis and analysing what was necessary.
D	I focused on firmly understanding all the project members. Not just remembering names and majors but also trying to determine at an early stage what kind of human beings they were. As a result, in group activities, it was possible to work after knowing the other person's situation, thus increasing the probability of success.	When trying to prototype the system considered by the project members, the members' roles became vague. Therefore, to make the best use of the characteristics of each department, we made a place to share knowledge of the field of each member, and all members decided to deepen mutual understanding. Then project progress became smoother.

7. CONCLUSION

Leadership education has been conducted for first-year students of the Master's program of Systems Engineering and Science for over ten years. The program has five modules: knowledge, training by simulation, real action, reflection, and assessment.

This program has been made compulsory and is attended by many students (about 80). It became necessary to devise a way of reflection to produce educational effects for the large numbers of students. Consequently, we introduced peer reflection – the students exchanged reflections with each other based on behaviour recorded in their e-portfolios. Students who tried to continually apply the new learning obtained by peer reflection in a real situation significantly improved their leadership behaviour.

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